

Proof of a postulate of Euclidean geometry

Postulate. Considering a point A belonging to a plane, infinite lines pass through it, also defined as a bundle of lines.

Proof. Consider the equation of the line in explicit form that passes through a Cartesian plane with center 0 at the origin of the x and y axes:

$$y = mx + q$$

Because the line passes through the point with coordinates (0, 0), we have $q=0$. So the equation becomes:

$$y = mx$$

Because $m \in \mathbb{R}$ and the set of real numbers is infinite, m can assume infinite values. Q.E.D.